

Magnetic and magnetocaloric properties of $\text{YCr}_{0.85}\text{Mn}_{0.15}\text{O}_3$ orthochromites

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Abstract

Orthochromites have attracted significant attention of the researchers due to their interesting properties like temperature induced magnetization reversal (TIMR), exchange bias (EB), spin reorientation (SR) and magnetocaloric effect (MCE) along with their potential applications in spintronics, thermally assisted random access memory and magnetic refrigeration devices [1-2]. We have investigated structural, magnetic and magnetocaloric properties of manganese (Mn) doped $\text{YCr}_{0.85}\text{Mn}_{0.15}\text{O}_3$ (YCMO) polycrystalline compound which possesses orthorhombic unit cell with *Pnma* space group. EDX analysis confirmed the basic constituents of YCMO compound. The compound showed the Neel temperature (T_N) \sim 132 K, lower than that for pristine YCO sample. It also exhibited negative magnetization around 52 K in field cooled (FC) mode. The magnetic entropy change, $(-\Delta S) \sim 0.365 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ along with relative cooling power (RCP) $\sim 13.52 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$, was obtained near 36 K under an applied field of 9 T.

Keywords: Orthochromites, magnetization reversal, magnetocaloric effect

References

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- [2] S. Kumar et al, J. Appl. Phys. 121 (2017) 043907.